

Speculation on Quantum Density Humps and Internal Motion

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In the literature (1), it is argued that a correspondence principle holds with a classical density $dx/v = dt$ roughly matching the envelope of the humps (peaks) of a quantum single particle bound state density $W(x)W(x)$. (For example, quantum oscillator wavefunctions have such humps of varying height.). If a velocity argument $dt=dx/v$ is used to account for differences in hump heights, it seems a velocity argument should also account for the hump densities themselves. If one considers the free particle wavefunctions $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$, however, the average kinetic energy is: $\frac{p^2}{2m} \frac{[\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)]}{[\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)]} = \frac{p^2}{2m}$ which together with $p_{rms}=p$ yields a classical picture. With $\frac{p^2}{2m}$ and p_{rms} , the density humps cannot be accounted for. For example, a particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls has a wavefunction $B[\exp(ipave x) + \exp(-ipave x)]$. If one calculates $p_{ave} = ip \frac{\exp(ipx) - \exp(-ipx)}{[\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)]}$, a nonzero and purely imaginary result is obtained. " p_{ave} " is not the classical p_{rms} from $\frac{p^2}{2m}$, nor is it zero as would be expected for a simple $p-p$ sum which appears in both classical and classical statistical mechanics. Thus, there appears to be non-translational motion, due to the imaginary i , based on the magnitude of p and on periodicity also based on p i.e. $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. This motion contributes to the quantum bound spatial density change i.e. $\frac{d}{dx}(WW) = 2W \frac{dW}{dx}$ where $-i \frac{dW}{dx} / W = \langle p_{ave} \text{ at } x \rangle$. The change in spatial density from one point to another (i.e. the hump features) are due to this imaginary average motion which is linked to some kind of non-translational motion not necessarily internal motion of a particle. In particular, $\langle KE_{ave} \text{ at } x \rangle + V(x) = E$, so average kinetic energy is associated with motion related to $V(x)$ and there exists a conservation of energy equation for this kind of motion.

In this note, we investigate these ideas and provide an expression linking the quantum bound state change in density to $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$ and to the correspondence principle i.e. classical density based on $dt=dx/v(x)$. We also suggest that Force is related to motion as it is directly linked to $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$.

Density from Classical Mechanics and Correspondence Principle

Spatial density is not usually employed to describe bound state classical mechanical motion for a single particle e.g. a particle attached to a spring. The particle has various velocity values at different x points due to acceleration. In the literature (1), it is argued that if one dimensional space is divided into equal dx units, dt differs for each according to $dt = dx/v(x)$ where $\frac{1}{2}mv(x)^2 + V(x) = E$. " dt " is proportional to a spatial density which roughly forms an envelope for the peaks of a quantum bound state spatial density of $W(x)W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. $W(x)W(x)$ still may have humps which are not part of the envelope. Thus, a velocity (or time) based argument is made for the differing heights of the humps of $W(x)W(x)$. It seems a velocity argument should then account for the structure of the humps in order to have consistency. Such a velocity or momentum, however, is not expected to follow form $\frac{p^2}{2m} + V(x) = E$ which describes classical translational motion.

Positive and Negative Momentum Plane Waves

In classical statistical mechanical equilibrium with or without $V(x)$, one has equal probability for p and $-p$ at x . The average is 0 and one proceeds to calculate average $pp/2m$ and obtains a root-mean-square velocity. For a particle with no potential, the probability is the same for any x and is described by a real, positive number.

For a free quantum particle, one expects probability for any x to also be constant. If one has a potential $V(x)$, however, statistical scattering occurs from $V(x)$ and not from two particle collisions. The quantum bound state system has only one bound particle in this example. One may expect a momentum distribution at each x as a result. We have argued in a previous note (2) that such behaviour is consistent with a form of $\exp(ipx)$ for a free quantum particle and that there exists an unusual imaginary average momentum $-i d/dx \ln(W)$ in the quantum system. Even for a free particle, a non-classical interference pattern arises when it interacts with the potential associated with a two slit system. Nevertheless, it is often argued in quantum mechanics that the momentum and kinetic energy of a free quantum particle are p and pp respectively.

If one examines $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ for p and $-p$, one may calculate the average kinetic energy and momentum with no phase difference i.e. equal weights for $\exp(\pm ipx)$.

$$\text{Average kinetic energy} = pp/2m (\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)) / (\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)) = pp/2m \quad ((1a))$$

The average kinetic energy satisfies the classical result $pp/2m = E$ as does its root mean momentum. This picture is classical and translational.

$$\text{Average momentum} = p (\exp(ipx) - \exp(-ipx)) / (\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)) = 2ip \sin(px) \quad ((1b))$$

This result is purely imaginary suggesting motion other than translational related to $KE+V(x) = E$, but is still based on p , both in magnitude and in spatial frequency ($\sin(px)$). Nevertheless, ((1b)) is not classical or classical statistical. In classical physics, one expects an average of p and $-p$ to yield 0. Furthermore, ((1b)) suggests a pocket of forward motion followed by one of negative within the wavelength L where $p=2\pi/L$. It seems some kind of periodic motion exists associated with "imaginary" momentum. At first, one might ignore this average momentum as it is imaginary. It seems, however, that it is key as it governs the behaviour of probability and spatial density in quantum mechanics.

Extension to a System with a Potential

For a single bound particle in a potential $V(x)$, one may imagine an ensemble of $\exp(ipx)$ at x instead of a single $\exp(ipx)$ i.e.

$$W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

In addition, one may form averages using $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx) / W(x)$ i.e.

$$\langle p^2 \rangle = [\text{Sum over } p \quad p^2/2m P(p/x)] \quad \text{and} \quad \langle p \rangle = [\text{Sum over } p \quad p P(p/x)]$$

with: $\frac{1}{2m} \langle p^2 \rangle + V(x) = E$. There is again average classical motion and a $\langle p \rangle = \sqrt{\langle p^2 \rangle}$.

Additionally, however, one has $\langle p \rangle$ which is purely imaginary and governs the translation of $W(x)$ i.e.:

$$W(x+dx) = W(x) \exp(i \langle p \rangle dx) \quad ((3)) \quad \text{where} \quad \langle p \rangle = -i \frac{d}{dx} \ln(W)$$

Considering a bound state spatial density, this too is governed by $\langle p \rangle$ i.e.

$$\frac{d}{dx} W^2 = 2 W \frac{d}{dx} \ln(W) = W^2 \frac{d}{dx} \ln[W^2] \quad ((4))$$

In either case ((3)) or ((4)), it is $\frac{d}{dx} \ln(W)$ which accounts for the change in $W(x)$ or spatial density with x , but both have “hump” like behaviour, so it is the periodic $\langle p \rangle$ which “creates” this quantum hump like structure by changing $W(x)$ according to the periodic value of $\frac{d}{dx} \ln(W)$. The periodicity (forward-backward motion) of $\frac{d}{dx} \ln(W)$ leads to humps which represent spatial resolution. It is, however, an average i.e. $\langle p \rangle$ which yields the result, nevertheless it is based on motion. If one considers the classical density described in the first section:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \text{density} = C \frac{d}{dx} \ln(v) \quad ((5))$$

If $\langle p \rangle$ from $\langle KE \rangle + V(x) = E$, one may ask what extra motion is present in the system? First, even though ((4)) and ((5)) are of similar form $\frac{d}{dx} \ln(v)$ is related to:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \text{Density proportional to: } \frac{dv}{dt} / v = \text{Force} / v \quad (\text{for } m=1) \quad ((6))$$

while $\frac{d}{dx} \ln(W) = i \langle p \rangle$. because $\langle p \rangle = -i \frac{d}{dx} \ln W$

Taking $\frac{d}{dx}$ of the time-independent Schrodinger equation:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \text{density proportional to } \langle p \rangle = [E - V(x)] / \langle p \rangle \quad ((7))$$

Where $E - V(x) = \langle p^2 \rangle / 2m$ which is usually smooth e.g. $E - \frac{1}{2} kx^2$ for an oscillator

For a classical system $\langle p \rangle = \langle p^2 \rangle / 2m = 0$ because one has p and $-p$ or $-p^2$ and p^2 , but in the quantum situation neither $\langle p \rangle$ nor $\langle p^2 \rangle$ are zero. Otherwise, ((6)) and ((7)) are very similar. A difference between the two, however, is that $\frac{dv}{dt}$ is related to smooth motion describing an envelope over humps of $W(x)W(x)$ while $\langle p \rangle$ is periodic leading to a periodic $W(x)$ and a spatial density of humps characteristic of quantum mechanics. ((7)) contains a leading term which is essentially the classical result and a second quantum mechanical term

$\langle p^2 \rangle / [E - V(x)]$. ((7)) seems to describe the correspondence principle as the first term is strictly classical in form. The periodicity of $\langle p \rangle$ should arise from $\langle p^2 \rangle$. $\langle p \rangle$ is proportional to a change in density, so the first term accounts for the change in the heights of the humps (peaks), while the second accounts for the structure (periodicity) of the humps themselves. $\langle p \rangle$ should be an average momentum, but the first term is $F(x) / (E - V(x))$ i.e. a force or d/dx of $V(x)$ divided by kinetic energy. It is unusual that force should be proportional to an average momentum. In classical physics it is related to d momentum/ dt . One way to see how force may be related to an average momentum is to consider the potential as:

$$V(x) = \sum V(k) \exp(ikx) \text{ then Force}(x) = -d/dx V(x) = -\sum V(k) ik \exp(ikx) \quad ((8))$$

In such a situation, force has the form of an average momentum in quantum mechanics. In other words $V(x)$ is an average potential which has a physical structure. This structure is also periodic if one uses $\exp(ikx)$ which may represent virtual photons. The term $F(x)/[E - V(x)]$, however, has no periodic structure. Thus, extra non-translational back and forth motion may occur which we argue leads to the peak-trough behaviour in quantum mechanics.

Conclusion

If the classical density for a single bound particle is taken to be $C dx / v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is velocity and according to the correspondence principle this describes an envelope roughly through the peaks of $W(x)W(x)$, we suggest that velocity or momentum considerations should account for the quantum hump structure as well. We argue that if $\exp(ipx)$ represents a free particle, average kinetic energy for $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ is $p^2/2m$ and rms $p = p$ just as in classical physics, but there is also an unusual momentum average $= 2i p \cos(px)$ which is purely imaginary. This does not exist in classical or classical statistical mechanics where momentum average at each point is 0. This unusual momentum average accounts for the change in $W(x)$ the wavefunction and also spatial density $W(x)W(x)$. If this unusual momentum average is periodic it may give rise to hump structure in density which is characteristic of quantum mechanics. In the literature, some argue for internal motion such as zitterbewegung, but it seems that perhaps an external forced periodic motion (as in classical vibrations) could also yield such a scenario with $\langle p^2 \rangle$ describing a kind of classical mechanical motion related to $1/2m \langle p^2 \rangle + V(x) = E$ which is part of a system which also other motion. We give an expression linking d/dx density to $\langle p \rangle = F/KE(x) + \langle p^2 \rangle / 2m$. The first term is classical and is identical to the correspondence principle. Furthermore, $F(x)$ should behave as an average velocity if it is equated with other terms to $\langle p \rangle$. A picture in which $V(x) = \sum \text{over } k V(k) \exp(ikx)$ yields such a scenario. This scenario may be based on virtual photons and may involve forward and backward motion which is non-translational.

References

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